

Development of Monte Carlo Estimators of the Flux Gradient for the GUARDYAN GPU Based Dynamic Monte Carlo Code

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ABSTRACT

Monte Carlo codes are routinely used for producing the group constants for deterministic solvers including the diffusion coefficient. For the proper calculation of diffusion coefficients it is often mentioned that neutron current weighting should be applied to the transport cross section instead of the widespread weighting by the neutron flux, but it is scarcely noted that if we follow the multi-group formulation of the P1 and diffusion equations then the diffusion coefficients themselves ought to be weighted by the gradient of the neutron flux. Recently we explored the possibility of estimating the neutron flux gradient in a Monte Carlo transport simulation in order to use the group flux gradients when collapsing the group diffusion coefficients from some micro-group structure to some macro-group structure. In this paper we introduce two methods developed to estimate approximate gradients in Monte Carlo particle transport simulations and present some proof-of-concept simulations along with preliminary results of the methods as implemented into the GPU based dynamic Monte Carlo code GUARDYAN.

Keywords: Monte Carlo, diffusion coefficient, flux gradient, estimators, GUARDYAN

1. INTRODUCTION

Most modern production grade Monte Carlo codes such as Serpent 2 [1] or OpenMC [2] are equipped with some group constant production capabilities [3] [4]. The GPU based dynamic Monte Carlo neutron transport code GUARDYAN has been in development at the Institute of Nuclear Techniques of the Budapest University of Technology and Economics since about 2015. The code is written in C++ using CUDA and over the years the basic functionality of a neutron transport code have been implemented, verified [5], and validated [6] [7]. In recent years, apart from more theoretical research such as the modelling of Monte Carlo transport for stability studies [8] or investigating the feasibility of exotic variance reduction techniques [9], the emphasis of the development team was on extending the capabilities of GUARDYAN, e.g.: in order to include the temperature feedbacks in our simulations the subchannel thermal hydraulics solver SUBCHANFLOW has been coupled to GUARDYAN [10] and used for the simulation of rod ejection transients [11], and recently group constant production capabilities have been implemented into GUARDYAN as well.

Among the group constants GUARDYAN is set out to generate diffusion coefficients are the most cumbersome. Currently the approach is to estimate the transport cross section in the user defined energy structure and simply use the reciprocal. More sophisticated approaches exist which collapse the reciprocal transport cross section [3], and the cumulative migration method [12] that takes an entirely different approach should also be mentioned. In any case, there are two things worth to note when producing group constants: the correct weighting of the transport cross section is with the neutron current, and

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the correct weighting of the diffusion coefficient is with the gradient of the neutron flux. Both of these are clear if one looks at the second P1 equation and Fick's law, shown in Equations (1)

$$\Sigma_t(\underline{r}, E)\underline{J}(\underline{r}, E) + \frac{1}{3}\underline{\nabla}\Phi(\underline{r}, E) = \int_0^{\infty} \Sigma_{s1}(\underline{r}, E' \rightarrow E)\underline{J}(\underline{r}, E')dE' \Rightarrow \underline{J}(\underline{r}, E) = -D(\underline{r}, E)\underline{\nabla}\Phi(\underline{r}, E) \quad (1)$$

and it is also briefly mentioned both in relevant journal papers [3] and textbooks [13]. Concerning the transport cross section and its weighting the overall sentiment is that reliable Monte Carlo neutron current estimates are hard to produce and using the (strictly speaking) incorrect flux weighting results in less inaccuracies overall, which is a fair assessment in our experience as well.

Regarding the diffusion coefficient, if one decides to arrange the second P1 equation to the form of Fick's law without the usual assumptions necessary for the actual transition to the diffusion approximation, will end up with Equation (2)

$$\underline{J}(\underline{r}, E) = -\frac{1}{3} \left[\Sigma_t(\underline{r}, E) - \frac{\int_0^{\infty} \Sigma_{s1}(\underline{r}, E' \rightarrow E)\underline{J}(\underline{r}, E')dE'}{\underline{J}(\underline{r}, E)} \right]^{-1} \underline{\nabla}\Phi(\underline{r}, E) \quad (2)$$

it is clear that there is no convenient closed form expression for the diffusion coefficient that could be used for the Monte Carlo estimation of a reaction rate type quantity in order to produce the group diffusion coefficients, and that is without mentioning the fact that the equation contains a division by a vector, that is nonsensical without further assumptions [13].

Instead if we follow the methodology applied by Serpent [3] that collapses micro-group fluxes and group constants estimated on a fine energy structure in order to produce the macro-group group constants for a coarser energy structure desired by the user, then collapsing the reciprocal of the micro-group transport cross sections to get the macro-group diffusion coefficients might as well be done by weighting them with the micro-group neutron flux gradients. In this paper we introduce 2 methods we developed for the estimation of (approximate) gradients using Monte Carlo methods and their implementation specifically for Monte Carlo particle transport simulations. In Section 2 the estimators are derived, followed by their implementation into 3D Monte Carlo particle transport codes discussed in Section 3. Sections 4 and 5 elaborate on the testing of the estimators with some preliminary results from GUARDYAN as well, followed by Section 6 summarising our experiences.

2. MONTE CARLO ESTIMATION OF GRADIENTS

In this section we will introduce the (approximate) gradient estimators we developed for GUARDYAN in a general context focusing on the mathematics in one dimension. The actual implementation for a particle transport code and the 3D formulation of the estimators will be discussed in Section 3. The estimate of quantities will be denoted by a tilde, with the method of estimation specified in superscript.

2.1. Linear Detector Function Estimator

The first method we developed is quite straightforward: the function $f(x)$ is multiplied by some $D(x)$ detector function so that

$$\frac{df(x)}{d(x)} \approx \int_a^b D(x)f(x)dx; \quad \text{where} \quad D(x) = D_{LDF}(x) = A \frac{x - \frac{b+a}{2}}{b-a} \quad (3)$$

The detector function is a linear function on the domain $[a; b]$ scaled to go from $D_{LDF}(a) = -1$ to $D_{LDF}(b) = 1$, hence we decided to call the method the *Linear Detector Function* or *LDF* estimator. The use of a linear function to approximate the first derivative, apart from being intuitive, can be justified by first expanding $f(x)$ by Legendre polynomials as shown in Equation (4)

$$f(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} c_n f_n P_n(x); \quad \text{where} \quad f_n = \frac{1}{c_n} \int_{-1}^1 f(x) P_n(x) dx; \quad \text{and} \quad c_n = \frac{2n+1}{2} \quad (4)$$

where $P_n(x)$ is the n -th order Legendre polynomial, f_n is the n -th expansion coefficient and c_n is the normalisation factor of the n -th order Legendre polynomial. Let us now take the first derivative of this approximation:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{df(x)}{dx} &= \frac{d}{dx} \left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} c_n f_n P_n(x) \right) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} c_n f_n \frac{d}{dx} P_n(x) = \\ &= c_0 f_0 \frac{d}{dx} 1 + c_1 f_1 \frac{d}{dx} x + c_2 f_2 \frac{d}{dx} \left[\frac{1}{2} (3x^2 - 1) \right] + \dots = \\ &= c_1 f_1 + 3x c_2 f_2 + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

keeping the first term that does not vanish upon differentiation we have

$$\frac{df(x)}{dx} \approx c_1 f_1 = \frac{1}{c_1} \int_{-1}^1 f(x) P_1(x) dx = \frac{1}{c_1} \int_{-1}^1 f(x) x dx \quad (6)$$

which when shifted and scaled to an arbitrary $[a; b]$ yields $D_{LDF}(x)$ introduced in Equation (3).

The only step remaining is the calculation of the normalisation factor A , carried out in Equation (7) where we require that the LDF estimate of an arbitrary linear function $f(x) = B + Cx$ is equivalent to its derivative integrated over the domain $[a; b]$.

$$\begin{aligned} \int_a^b \left[\frac{d}{dx} (B + Cx) \right] dx &= A \cdot \int_a^b \left(\frac{x - \frac{b+a}{2}}{b-a} \right) (B + Cx) dx \Rightarrow \frac{\int_a^b C dx}{\int_a^b \left(\frac{x - \frac{b+a}{2}}{b-a} \right) (B + Cx) dx} = \\ &= \frac{C(b-a)}{\frac{1}{b-a} \left[\frac{Bx^2}{2} + \frac{Cx^3}{3} - \frac{B(b+a)x}{2} - \frac{C(b+a)x^2}{4} \right]_a^b} = \frac{(b-a)^2}{\left(\frac{b^3-a^3}{3} - \frac{b^3+ab^2-ba^2-a^3}{4} \right)} = \frac{12}{(b-a)} = A \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Furthermore, if we are interested in an average over $[a; b]$ instead of an integral, a division with the volume must also be included, for the 1D case with $V = b - a$ we end up with Equation (8).

$$\frac{d\widetilde{f(x)}^{LDF}}{dx} = \frac{1}{(b-a)} \frac{12}{(b-a)} \int_a^b \frac{x - \frac{b+a}{2}}{(b-a)} f(x) dx = \frac{12}{(b-a)^3} \int_a^b \left(x - \frac{b+a}{2}\right) f(x) dx \quad (8)$$

2.2. Midpoint Method Estimator

The second approach we established is based on the simple numeric approximation of the derivative of $f(x)$ at x_0 with the *symmetric difference quotient* [14] shown in Equation (9) using the neighbouring points $x_0 \pm \frac{\Delta x}{2}$ i.e. we are looking for a derivative at the middle of a section, hence why we decided to call the technique the *midpoint method* or *MPM* estimator.

$$\left. \frac{df(x)}{dx} \right|_{x_0} \approx \frac{f\left(x_0 + \frac{\Delta x}{2}\right) - f\left(x_0 - \frac{\Delta x}{2}\right)}{\Delta x} \quad (9)$$

As we did in Section 2.1 we will derive the estimator for some arbitrary $[a; b]$ domain. Substituting $\Delta x = b - a$ into Equation (9) and integrating over $[a; b]$ immediately yields Equation (10)

$$\begin{aligned} \int_a^b \frac{df(x)}{dx} dx &\approx \int_a^b \frac{1}{b-a} \left[f\left(x + \frac{b-a}{2}\right) - f\left(x - \frac{b-a}{2}\right) \right] dx = \\ &= \frac{1}{b-a} \left[\int_a^b f\left(x + \frac{b-a}{2}\right) dx - \int_a^b f\left(x - \frac{b-a}{2}\right) dx \right] = \frac{1}{b-a} \left[\int_{a+\frac{b-a}{2}}^{b+\frac{b-a}{2}} f(x) dx - \int_{a-\frac{b-a}{2}}^{b-\frac{b-a}{2}} f(x) dx \right] \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Since we are interested in an average, a division by the volume ($b - a$ in 1D) is also to be included, resulting in Equation (11)

$$\frac{d\widetilde{f(x)}^{MPM}}{dx} = \frac{1}{(b-a)^2} \left[\int_{a+\frac{b-a}{2}}^{b+\frac{b-a}{2}} f(x) dx - \int_{a-\frac{b-a}{2}}^{b-\frac{b-a}{2}} f(x) dx \right] \quad (11)$$

3. IMPLEMENTATION FOR TRANSPORT SIMULATIONS

In 3D the gradient components in each direction are estimated separately using the appropriate position coordinate of the neutrons. The LDF and MPM methods are implemented as collision estimators as it is a well established method and GUARDYAN already used it exclusively, although there is nothing that inherently prohibits the use of other flux estimators.

In this current section Δx , Δy , and Δz will refer to the user defined voxel sizes of volume $\Delta V = \Delta x \Delta y \Delta z$, and P is used to denote all phase space coordinates together when it is convenient. The estimates are also normalised by the number of neutrons N .

The LDF estimator as derived in Equation (8) is trivial to implement: the flux contribution of a collision is multiplied by the value of the linear detector function at its position. Separate tallies are kept for the x , y , and z components of the gradient using the appropriate position coordinate of the particles. The final form of the estimator for the x component is shown in Equation (12) where the internal logic of GUARDYAN, shared by the 3D proof-of-concept code, for storing grids is used: x_{min} is the starting

coordinate in the x direction of the first voxel, n_x is the index in the x direction of the voxel that the particle falls in. The other directions are calculated in an analogous manner.

$$\widetilde{\nabla\Phi}_x^{LDF} = \frac{12}{N\Delta V\Delta x^2} \sum_{P_j \in \Delta P_i} \left[x_j - x_{min} - \left(n_x + \frac{1}{2} \right) \Delta x \right] \frac{w_j}{\Sigma_{tot}(\mathbf{r}_j, E_j)} \quad (12)$$

The MPM estimator is in a way still simpler, it is only a flux estimator on an appropriate grid and some post processing. The flux is estimated on a Cartesian grid with double the resolution of the gradient estimation itself and results from 8 voxels are used to calculate the gradient components at the point in the middle where their corners meet, i.e. the midpoint of the *user defined* voxels. This is illustrated in Figure 1 where the 8 smaller voxels are labelled from the one closest to the origin.

We are using flux estimates on a grid with $(b - a)/2$ step size, so we are technically estimating the flux gradient for the cube around the midpoint with $(b - a)/2$ side length and use that as the estimate for the whole user specified voxel. This is in order to keep the MPM and LDF methods comparable by only using samples from the $[a; b]$ interval, but with this same flux tally we could also approximate the flux gradient for the $(b - a)/2$ sections overlapping the boundaries of the larger grid.

Figure 1. Illustration how the MPM estimator uses fluxes of 8 sub-voxels.

To estimate the gradient in a given direction the fluxes of the voxels are averaged in the perpendicular plane, e.g. the x component of the gradient is calculated with the MPM method as in Equation (13) where the notations for the voxels follow Figure 1. The other components calculated in an analogue manner.

$$\widetilde{\nabla\Phi}_x^{MPM} = \frac{2 \left[\frac{1}{4} (\tilde{\Phi}_E + \tilde{\Phi}_F + \tilde{\Phi}_G + \tilde{\Phi}_H) - \frac{1}{4} (\tilde{\Phi}_A + \tilde{\Phi}_B + \tilde{\Phi}_C + \tilde{\Phi}_D) \right]}{\Delta x} \quad (13)$$

Where the fluxes are estimated on the finer mesh with a collision estimator i.e.:

$$\tilde{\Phi}_i = \frac{1}{N\Delta V_i} \sum_{P_j \in \Delta P_i} \frac{w_j}{\Sigma_{tot}(\mathbf{r}_j, E_j)}; \quad \text{with} \quad \Delta V_i = \frac{\Delta x}{2} \frac{\Delta y}{2} \frac{\Delta z}{2} = \frac{\Delta V}{8} \quad (14)$$

4. TESTING

For the initial testing a 1D monoenergetic transport model developed by Hoogenboom [15] was used, this consisted of 2 homogeneous regions: region $I.$, also containing a homogeneous source, is between $-a$ and a with $\Sigma_a^{I.} = 0.55 \frac{1}{\text{cm}}$ and $\Sigma_{tot}^{I.} = 1 \frac{1}{\text{cm}}$, and is surrounded by region $II.$ ($|x| > a$) with $\Sigma_a^{II.} =$

$0.1 \frac{1}{\text{cm}}$ and $\Sigma_{tot}^{II} = 0.5 \frac{1}{\text{cm}}$. A simple 3D model with these same parameters was then considered, this contained a cube with side length $2a$ around the origin as region *I*. and region *II*. was $1000a$ thick instead of infinite due to running times. While in the 1D case the same anisotropic scattering was used as in [15], in the 3D case we opted to keep it isotropic for simplicity. Implicit capture with Russian roulette was used in both 1D and 3D cases, and the free path was sampled by Woodcock(-delta) tracking.

The 1D Monte Carlo simulations were run with a single cycle of 10^6 particles, the 3D simulation used 100 cycles of 10^5 particles to reach a sufficiently low statistical uncertainty. The results were tallied on grids with 1 cm step sizes.

For the GUARDYAN preliminary test a single homogeneous cube surrounded by vacuum was used, which was filled with a material containing about a dozen of isotopes including U-235 and U-238, set to $k_{eff} = 1$ by modifying the side length. The results were tallied in a 10-by-10-by-10 Cartesian grid.

5. RESULTS

In Figures 2-4 the results of the gradient estimators for the test models discussed in Section 4 can be seen, while Figure 5 shows the preliminary results of the estimators as implemented in GUARDYAN. The 2D plots show the x component of the gradient at the middle axial layer in the z direction.

Figure 2. Comparison of the flux and flux derivative estimates with the analytical solution in 1D.

The solution for the 1D case can be given analytically [15], providing us with a suitable reference used in Figure 2 to show the agreement with the estimators we developed.

Figure 3. Flux and flux gradient estimates calculated for the 3D model.

Figures 3 and 4 are showing the results of the 3D tests and have no analytical references. Even so the gradient components follow the expected tendency, especially if we compare Figure 3 recorded at around the x axis in 3D with the proper 1D results shown in Figure 2.

Finally some preliminary GUARDYAN results are shown in Figure 5 which serve more as a proof of

Figure 4. Flux and flux gradient estimates calculated for the 3D model.

Figure 5. Preliminary results of the GUARDYAN implementation of the estimators.

concept, than anything more solid, but suggest that the estimators are feasible in a fully complex neutron transport simulation as well.

6. CONCLUSIONS

We introduced two methods to estimate an approximate neutron flux gradient in a Monte Carlo particle transport simulation and implemented them in simplified Monte Carlo particle transport codes. The estimators were compared to analytical solutions in 1D and tested on a basic 3D model with the results showing an agreement with the expectations. The methods were then implemented into the GUARDYAN GPU based dynamic neutron transport code, with which preliminary results suggest that the method gives correct results in a fully complex neutron transport as well. Although the initial results are promising the practical utility and stability of the estimators should be investigated.

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